

User Satisfaction with Assistive Devices among Persons with Lower-Limb Amputation in Udaipur District, Rajasthan: A Cross-Sectional Study**Sneha J. Patil¹, Rajesh Kumar Chaudhary², Poonam Prakash³, Aditya Prakash⁴, Jatin Prajapati⁵, Deepak Kumar Ninama⁶, Prachi Khandelwal⁷**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, GMERS Medical College, Valsad, Gujarat, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation, Government Medical College, Banswara, Rajasthan, India³MBBS, Ananta Institute of Medical Sciences & Research Centre, Rajsamand, Rajasthan, India⁴PG student, Department of Community Medicine, Government Medical College, Dungarpur, Rajasthan, India^{5,6}PG student, Department of Community Medicine, RNT Medical College, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India⁷PG student, Department of Ophthalmology, RNT Medical College, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India

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Corresponding author: Dr. Jatin Prajapati

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Abstract**Background:** Lower-limb amputation results in significant functional limitations, affecting mobility, independence, and quality of life. Assistive devices such as prostheses and orthoses play a critical role in restoring functional ability. Understanding user satisfaction and associated socio-demographic factors is essential for improving rehabilitation outcomes.**Objectives:** To assess satisfaction with assistive devices among persons with lower-limb amputation in Udaipur district, Rajasthan, and to identify socio-demographic factors influencing these parameters.**Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted among 106 individuals with lower-limb amputation in Udaipur between January and June 2024. Participants were selected using systematic random sampling. Data were analyzed using SPSS v25. Satisfaction was assessed with the Quebec User Evaluation of Satisfaction with Assistive Technology (QUEST 2.0), defining satisfaction as a mean score ≥ 4 . Device (8 items) and service (4 items) subscales were analyzed separately, and multivariate logistic regression was performed with satisfaction as the dependent variable; $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.**Results:** Among the 106 participants, 73.6% were male, and the majority were aged 45-59 years (35.8%). Most participants (60.4%) resided in rural areas, and 26.4% were unemployed. Prosthetic limb usage was reported by 67.9%, while 9.4% used orthotic devices. The overall QUEST mean score was 3.82 ± 0.85 , with 79.0% of participants satisfied (score ≥ 4). Satisfaction with the device subscale was moderate (mean 3.73 ± 0.87 ; 76.8% satisfied), with highest ratings for safety and ease of use, and lower ratings for comfort and weight. The service subscale showed higher satisfaction (mean 4.0 ± 0.8 ; 82.1% satisfied), particularly for service delivery and follow-up. Major barriers included high maintenance costs (42.5%) and limited access to advanced devices (36.8%). On multivariate analysis, higher education (AOR 2.15, 95% CI 1.05–4.40) and employment (AOR 1.92, 95% CI 1.01–3.65) were independently associated with greater satisfaction, whereas age, gender, and residence showed no significant association.**Conclusion:** Most lower-limb amputees in Udaipur benefited from assistive devices, though challenges in comfort, affordability, and accessibility remain. Limitations include selection bias (only device users), cross-sectional design, and self-reported data. Policy efforts should focus on improving device quality, reducing costs, and expanding community-based rehabilitation services to optimize functional outcomes and user satisfaction.**Keywords:** Lower-limb amputation, Assistive devices, Prosthesis, Rehabilitation, User satisfaction.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Lower-limb amputation imposes profound physical, psychological, and social consequences, significantly diminishing mobility, autonomy, and

quality of life among affected individuals. Properly designed and fitted prosthetic devices are central to restoring ambulation and enabling participation in

activities of daily living (ADLs), yet their availability and effectiveness remain limited—especially in low- and middle-income countries such as India [1]. India's burden of disability is substantial. National-level estimates suggest that only one in ten individuals requiring assistive devices actually access them, highlighting a severe gap in coverage [1]. Among those with locomotor disabilities, only 3.9% reported use of an artificial limb, while 7.1% cited affordability as a key barrier to access [1]. These figures underscore the structural and socioeconomic challenges faced by amputees in securing essential rehabilitation technologies. One of the most culturally adaptable and cost-effective prosthetic devices developed in India is the Jaipur Foot. Engineered in 1969 by Dr. Pramod Karan Sethi and Ram Chandra Sharma, this innovative design allows users to squat, sit cross-legged, and walk barefoot—features that align with rural Indian lifestyles [2,3]. Its soft multi-axial ankle structure provides suitability for uneven terrain, though it may be less ideal for high-performance activities [3]. In comparative assessments, the Jaipur Foot demonstrated more natural gait mechanics than alternatives like SACH and Seattle feet, despite some trade-offs in shock absorption [4,5]. Moreover, durability studies show survival rates of 53% at 3 years, outperforming many low-income alternatives [6].

Despite these advantages, limitations in Jaipur Foot production quality persist. Studies highlight inconsistent manufacturing standards, material variability, and structural weaknesses—particularly along interfaces between heel and forefoot blocks—that may lead to premature failure [7,8]. Addressing these challenges remains crucial for increasing the device's functionality and longevity. Psychologically and socially, amputation triggers substantial adjustment challenges. India-based data indicate high rates of depression, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress disorders among amputees, with estimates ranging from 32% to 84% for psychiatric issues and 10% to 63% for depression alone [1]. Compounding these mental health concerns, amputees often face reduced employment opportunities due to functional limitations and stigma, further undermining their quality of life (QOL).

Several Indian cross-sectional studies illuminate the multidimensional impact of amputation. A tertiary center in northern India assessed quality of life among 106 unilateral lower-limb amputees using WHOQOL-BREF. Findings showed that physical functioning scored lowest, followed by environmental, psychological, and social domains. Delays in prosthetic fitting correlated with poorer physical outcomes, emphasizing the critical role of early rehabilitation [9]. Another study involving 88 Indian amputees explored demographic and clinical

factors, reporting a mean age of 39 years, predominance of male (75%) and rural (60%) participants, with trauma being the primary cause (66%). Transtibial amputations were most common (64%). Prosthesis usage was observed in only 40% of cases; stump-related complications such as phantom limb pain and ulcers affected nearly 21%, impeding device adoption [10]. Further, data from South India comparing prosthetic/orthotic users and individuals without disability reveal significantly lower QOL scores among users—especially in physical health, psychological well-being, and environmental domains. Socioeconomic indicators like income, education, and living in urban slums were strongly associated with worse outcomes [11]. Other broader studies corroborate the positive influence of prosthesis use on QOL. For example, a 2022 cross-sectional study using WHOQOL-BREF and Trinity Amputation and Prosthesis Experience Scales reported that nearly 48% of users had better QOL, with prosthesis use strongly associated with improved well-being; however, residual limb pain (53%) and phantom limb pain (37%) remained highly prevalent [12]. While these studies provide valuable insights at regional and institutional levels, there is a notable research gap regarding the Udaipur district of Rajasthan. Udaipur comprises a mix of urban and rural populations and is home to rehabilitation NGOs such as Narayan Seva Sansthan, which offers treatment and rehabilitation services for physical disabilities [13]. Yet, systematic data on assistive device user satisfaction in this district remain lacking. This study aims to address this gap by focusing on user satisfaction with assistive devices among persons with lower-limb amputation in Udaipur district. Through a cross-sectional design, it seeks to assess satisfaction using validated instruments, and explore influencing factors such as demographic characteristics, amputation etiology, and prosthesis type. Clarifying these patterns is essential for tailoring rehabilitation services, improving delivery mechanisms, and enhancing functional outcomes in this culturally and geographically distinct population.

Material and Methods

Study Design and Setting: This study was conducted as a community-based cross-sectional survey in the Udaipur district of Rajasthan, India. Data collection was carried out from January 2024 to June 2024.

The district was selected for its mixed urban–rural population and availability of rehabilitation services, including government hospitals, private rehabilitation centers, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) catering to amputees.

Study Population: The study population comprised individuals aged 18 years and above with unilateral or bilateral lower-limb amputation, residing in

Udaipur district for at least 6 months, and using at least one assistive device (e.g., prosthesis, orthosis, walking aid). Patients with congenital limb deficiency, non-user of any assistive device, severe cognitive impairment, or those unwilling to participate were excluded.

Sample Size Determination: The sample size was calculated using the formula for single proportion:

$$n = Z^2_{(1-\alpha/2)} \times p \times (1-p) / d^2$$

Where:

- $Z_{(1-\alpha/2)} = 1.96$ (for 95% confidence level)
- $p = 0.5$ (assumed proportion of satisfied users due to lack of local estimates)
- $d = 0.10$ (absolute precision of 10%)
- $n = (1.96)^2 \times 0.5 \times 0.5 / (0.10)^2 = 3.8416 \times 0.25 / 0.01 = 96.04$

Thus, the minimum required sample size was 96 participants. Considering a 10% non-response rate, the final sample size was 106 participants.

Sampling Technique: Systematic random sampling from facility registers technique was used. In the first stage, a list of all prosthetic and rehabilitation service providers in Udaipur district was obtained from the Department of Social Justice and Empowerment. In the second stage, eligible participants were identified from patient registers of these facilities. In the final stage, participants were selected using systematic random sampling until the required sample size was achieved.

Data Collection Tool

A structured, pre-tested questionnaire was used, divided into three sections:

1. Sociodemographic details (age, sex, education, occupation, income, residence, time since amputation, cause of amputation).
2. User satisfaction – assessed using the Quebec User Evaluation of Satisfaction with Assistive Technology (QUEST 2.0) scale, which includes 12 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale.

The questionnaire was translated into Hindi and back-translated to ensure accuracy. A pilot study

was conducted on 10 participants (excluded from the final sample) to refine the tool.

Data Collection Procedure: Data were collected through face-to-face interviews by trained field investigators. Interviews were conducted at participants' homes or rehabilitation centers, ensuring privacy and comfort. Written informed consent was obtained prior to participation.

Data Analysis: Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequencies, and percentages) were used to summarize sociodemographic and clinical variables.

The primary outcome of interest was satisfaction, assessed using the Quebec User Evaluation of Satisfaction with Assistive Technology (QUEST) 2.0 questionnaire, with satisfaction defined as a mean score ≥ 4 on the 5-point Likert scale. For detailed assessment, the device subscale (8 items) reflecting user satisfaction with the assistive device and the service subscale (4 items) reflecting satisfaction with related service delivery were analyzed separately. Multivariate logistic regression was performed with satisfaction (≥ 4 vs. < 4) as the dependent variable and sociodemographic and clinical characteristics as independent variables, and associations were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical Considerations: Participants were informed about the purpose of the study, assured of confidentiality, and given the right to withdraw at any time without consequences. Ethical approval was obtained from Institutional Ethics Committee of RNT Medical College, Udaipur (No. RNT/ACAD/IEC/2023/850 dated 28/11/2023)

Results

A total of 106 participants with lower-limb amputation were included in the study. The majority were aged 45–59 years (35.8%), male (73.6%), and from rural areas (60.4%). Most had secondary education (30.2%) and were employed (35.8%). (Table 1)

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of study participants (n=106)

Variable	Category	n (%)
Age group (years)	18–29	14 (13.3)
	30–44	26 (24.5)
	45–59	38 (35.8)
	≥ 60	28 (26.4)
Gender	Male	78 (73.6)
	Female	28 (26.4)
Residence	Urban	42 (39.6)
	Rural	64 (60.4)
Education	Illiterate	20 (18.9)
	Primary	28 (26.4)

	Secondary	32 (30.2)
	Graduate & above	26 (24.5)
Occupation	Employed	38 (35.8)
	Unemployed	28 (26.4)
	Retired	16 (15.1)
	Student	6 (5.7)
	Homemaker	18 (17.0)

Transfemoral amputation was the most common level (56.5%), and trauma (54.7%) was the leading cause, followed by diabetes (24.5%). Prosthetic limbs were

the most frequently used assistive devices (67.9%). (Table 2)

Table 2: Distribution of Amputation Characteristics and Assistive Device Use among Participants (n=106)

Variable	Category	n (%)
Level of amputation	Transfemoral	60 (56.5)
	Transfemoral	34 (32.1)
	Knee disarticulation	6 (5.7)
	Others	6 (5.7)
Cause of amputation	Trauma	58 (54.7)
	Diabetes	26 (24.5)
	Peripheral vascular disease	12 (11.3)
	Tumor	6 (5.7)
	Other	4 (3.8)
Assistive device	Prosthetic limb	72 (67.9)
	Orthosis	10 (9.4)
	Crutches	14 (13.3)
	Wheelchair	10 (9.4)

The mean QUEST 2.0 device subscale score was 3.73 ± 0.87 , with 76.8% of participants satisfied (score ≥ 4). Among individual device-related items, the highest satisfaction was reported for safety (83.0%) and ease of use (80.2%), while the lowest was for comfort (71.7%) and weight (72.6%). The service subscale showed a higher overall satisfaction, with a mean score of 4.0 ± 0.8 and

82.1% of participants satisfied. Within this subscale, the highest satisfaction was noted for service delivery (83.0%) and follow-up services (82.6%). When both device and service components were combined, the overall QUEST mean score was 3.82 ± 0.85 , with 79.0% of participants reporting satisfaction. (Table 3).

Table 3: Mean Scores and Satisfaction Percentages for QUEST 2.0 Device and Service Subscales (n = 106)

QUEST Subscale	QUEST Item	Mean \pm SD	Satisfied (%)
Device Subscale	Dimensions	3.8 ± 0.9	78.3
	Weight	3.5 ± 1.0	72.6
	Adjustments	3.7 ± 0.8	75.5
	Safety	4.0 ± 0.7	83.0
	Durability	3.6 ± 0.9	74.5
	Ease of use	3.9 ± 0.8	80.2
	Comfort	3.5 ± 1.1	71.7
	Effectiveness	3.8 ± 0.8	78.3
Overall Device satisfaction (mean score)		3.73 ± 0.87	76.8
Service Subscale	Service delivery	4.1 ± 0.7	83.0
	Repairs/servicing	3.9 ± 0.8	81.1
	Professional services	4.0 ± 0.8	82.1
	Follow-up services	4.0 ± 0.7	82.6
Overall Service Satisfaction (mean score)		4.0 ± 0.8	82.1
Overall Satisfaction (mean score)		3.82 ± 0.85	79.0
QUEST= Quebec User Evaluation of Satisfaction with Assistive Technology; Satisfaction = QUEST ≥ 4			

Barriers to Assistive Devices Use

Figure 1: Major Barriers to Assistive Device Usage among Participants (n = 106)

The most frequently reported barriers were high maintenance costs (42.5%) and limited access to advanced devices (36.8%). Discomfort, aesthetics, and inadequate follow-up services were also noted, highlighting financial and service-delivery challenges as key obstacles in optimal assistive device utilization. (Figure 1).

On multivariate logistic regression, education level and employment status emerged as independent

predictors of satisfaction. Participants with education \geq secondary level were about twice as likely (AOR 2.15, 95% CI 1.05–4.40) to report high satisfaction, and those who were employed had nearly twofold higher odds of high satisfaction (AOR 1.92, 95% CI 1.01–3.65). Age, gender, and place of residence were not statistically significant predictors. (Table 4)

Table 4: Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis of Factors Associated with High Satisfaction

Variable	AOR	95% CI	p-value
Age (<45 years)	1.28	0.82 \pm 2.01	0.258
Gender (Male)	1.22	0.80 \pm 1.86	0.337
Urban residence	1.46	0.92 \pm 2.32	0.104
Education \geq Secondary	2.15	1.05 \pm 4.40	0.036*
Employment (Yes)	1.92	1.01 \pm 3.65	0.047*

AOR = Adjusted Odds Ratio; CI = Confidence Interval; Satisfaction = QUEST \geq 4; *Significant at $p < 0.05$

Discussion

The present study's findings on user satisfaction with assistive devices among lower-limb amputees demonstrate patterns both consistent with and divergent from prior research conducted in different settings and populations.

Sociodemographic profile: In the current study, the majority of participants were male (73.6%), aged 45–59 years, and from rural areas, with secondary education as the most common educational attainment.

This profile aligns partially with Garcez et al. [14], who also reported a predominance of males (81.8%) but with a younger age distribution (25–34 years being most represented). In contrast, the large-scale survey by DadeMatthews et al. [15] included a broader age range but was skewed toward younger participants (83.4% aged 19–39), and had a more diverse gender composition, including a small proportion of non-binary participants. The cause of amputation varied—trauma was the leading aetiology across all studies, representing 54.7% in our study, 78% in DadeMatthews et al.[15], and implied as a major contributor in Garcez et al.(14) This consistency reinforces trauma as a significant

cause of lower-limb amputation globally, though the proportion is influenced by study setting and population characteristics.

Level of amputation and device usage: Transtibial amputation was the most common in our study (56.5%) and also in DadeMatthews et al. [15] (39%), while Garcez et al. [14] did not explicitly quantify amputation levels but focused on long-term prosthesis users. Prosthetic limbs were the primary assistive devices in all studies, with our study reporting 67.9% prosthesis use, comparable to DadeMatthews et al. [15] where the study population was predominantly prosthesis users by inclusion criteria.

Satisfaction with prosthetic devices: Our study recorded high satisfaction for safety (mean 4.0 ± 0.7) and ease of use (3.9 ± 0.8), with overall satisfaction of 3.73 ± 0.87 (76.8% satisfied). Garcez et al. [14] reported slightly higher mean values for ease of use (4.3 ± 0.9) and efficacy (4.4 ± 0.8), but noted dissatisfaction with durability and comfort. DadeMatthews et al. [15] satisfaction levels, measured with the CSD scale, were lower overall (mean score 51.6/100), with major dissatisfaction related to skin irritation, comfort, pain, and maintenance cost. These variations may reflect differences in measurement tools, participant expectations, and healthcare delivery systems.

Satisfaction with services: In our study, the service subscale demonstrated relatively high satisfaction, with a mean score of 4.0 ± 0.8 and 82.1% of participants satisfied, particularly in the domains of service delivery and follow-up services. Education and employment were positively associated with higher satisfaction, underscoring the role of socioeconomic empowerment in shaping service perceptions. This contrasts with the findings of Garcez et al. [14], who reported very high satisfaction with professional services (mean 4.5 ± 1.2) but comparatively lower scores for repair and follow-up, suggesting variability in service quality across settings. Similarly, DadeMatthews et al. [15] documented lower overall service satisfaction (63%; CSS mean 51.9/100), with key concerns including prolonged wait times, difficulties in appointment scheduling, and limited involvement of users in decision-making.

Predictors of satisfaction: Across studies, device comfort, ease of use, and service quality consistently emerge as key determinants of satisfaction. In our study, while age, gender, and residence showed no significant association with satisfaction, both higher education (AOR 2.15, 95% CI 1.05–4.40, $p = 0.036$) and employment (AOR 1.92, 95% CI 1.01–3.65, $p = 0.047$) were independently associated with greater satisfaction. This suggests that socioeconomic empowerment enhances users' ability to access, adapt to, and benefit from assistive devices and

services. Garcez et al. [14] reported that device comfort and service quality were strongly correlated with physical health and multiple domains of quality of life, highlighting the interdependence of functionality, well-being, and satisfaction. Similarly, DadeMatthews et al. [15] used path analysis to demonstrate that functional performance (LEFS), balance confidence (ABC), and quality of life collectively explained 47% of the variance in device satisfaction and 34% of the variance in service satisfaction. These findings underscore that beyond device characteristics, physical functionality and psychosocial well-being play a pivotal role in shaping user experience. The alignment of our results with these studies reinforces the notion that improving both the technical quality of devices and the socioeconomic context of users is essential to achieving sustained satisfaction.

When viewed together, these studies underline the multifactorial nature of satisfaction with lower-limb prostheses, influenced by personal demographics, device performance, service delivery quality, functional ability, and psychosocial factors. Improving prosthesis comfort, enhancing patient involvement in care decisions, ensuring timely and accessible repair services, and addressing broader quality-of-life domains may yield substantial gains in both device and service satisfaction across diverse amputee populations. However, this study has certain limitations: selection bias may be present as only current device users were included, the cross-sectional design limits causal inferences, and reliance on self-reported data introduces potential reporting bias. Future research should address these issues by including non-users, employing longitudinal designs, and incorporating objective assessments of device performance and service quality.

Conclusion

This cross-sectional study conducted in Udaipur district among 106 persons with lower-limb amputation highlights the significant role of assistive devices in improving mobility, functional independence, and quality of life. The findings indicate varying levels of user satisfaction across different domains, including comfort, durability, aesthetics, and accessibility. Socio-demographic factors, particularly education and occupation were found to influence satisfaction levels. Despite the functional benefits reported, challenges remain—particularly regarding maintenance costs, limited availability of advanced devices, and the need for periodic adjustments. Many participants expressed a desire for better fitting, lighter weight, and more cosmetically appealing devices. The study underscores the importance of comprehensive rehabilitation services that address not only the provision of assistive devices but also user training, follow-up care, and counseling.

These results call for policymakers, rehabilitation centers, and NGOs in Rajasthan to prioritize equitable access to quality assistive devices and to strengthen community-based rehabilitation networks. By addressing existing barriers and tailoring interventions to user needs, rehabilitation services can enhance satisfaction, optimize functionality, and ultimately improve the participation and well-being of persons with lower-limb amputation in the region.

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